

Research Article

Combined Effect of Reinforced Katcha Fiber, Kerosene, and Natural Sand in Improving the Engineering Properties of Clay Soil

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This study investigates the impact of reinforcing weak subgrade clay soil (WSCS) from the Koye Feche road project in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, using natural fiber (katcha), kerosene, and sand. Various combinations of katcha fiber content (0.5%, 1%, and 1.5%), kerosene-soaked katcha fiber lengths (20, 35, and 50 mm), and sand percentages (10%, 15%, and 20%) were tested to determine their effects on the soil's performance. Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) tests were conducted to identify the optimum mix. Results indicate that the maximum UCS value is achieved with 1% katcha fiber content, 35 mm katcha fiber length, and 20% sand content. The plasticity of the optimum mix decreases to 31.46%, while its strength increases to 59.75% compared to the untreated subgrade clay soil. The reinforced soil demonstrates durability comparable to conventional materials, with a cost-saving of 40.71% over traditional replacement methods. This suggests the viability of reinforced soil in pavement construction, offering enhanced performance and economic benefits.

Keywords: katcha fiber; kerosene; reinforced soil; sand; weak subgrade

1. Introduction

The stability of any structure, including roads, is highly dependent on the strength properties of the underlying soil. The performance and pavement thickness of a road are directly influenced by the characteristics of the subgrade material, which is often composed of locally available soil deposits. In cases where these in situ conditions are unsuitable for supporting traffic loads, it is crucial to identify and implement cost-effective methods for improving the existing soil properties [1].

Ground modification techniques play a crucial role in addressing the challenges posed by weak soil properties. Among these techniques, reinforcement using fibers has gained prominence due to its effectiveness in enhancing specific soil characteristics such as shear strength, density, and hydraulic conductivity. The use of natural fibers in soil reinforcement is particularly noteworthy, as it offers significant environmental advantages and contributes to energy conservation.

This approach contrasts with traditional methods that rely heavily on synthetic fibers and industrial by-products, making it a more sustainable option for modern geotechnical engineering practices [2].

Kerosene and bitumen are widely used treatment mechanisms that physically prevent the entry of moisture into fiber. The study was conducted on the water absorption capacity (WAC) of kerosene-uncoated and kerosene-coated coir fibers, and it shows that the WAC of fiber is reduced from 58% to 100% for 2 and 9 days of a coir fiber soaked in kerosene, respectively [3]. Another study shows that similar behavior was observed in kerosene-coated coir fiber-reinforced expansive soil. The result shows maximum reduction for 2 and 3 days of soaked fiber. Two-day soaking reduces the WAC by 55.43%, and 3-day soaking reduced by 58.04% [4]. Research in Pakistan was conducted to improve the engineering characteristics of expansive clays by mixing sand in varying percentages from 5% to 35% with 5% intervals. The result shows that the swell potential and swell pressure of the soil decrease

from 3.5% to 0.5% and 90 kPa to 10 kPa, respectively, and the California Bearing Ratio (CBR) value increases from 4% to 8% for 30%–35% sand mixing [5].

Louafi and Bahar [6] studied sand as an additive for the stabilization of swelling clay soils. The result shows that an additive of sand 10–70 by 10% interval for stabilization of swelling clay soils reduces the consistency limit and swelling of clay soil, and the sand layer between two soil layers showed a substantial effect on the soil swell reduction. A similar study revealed that the sandy layer played a drainage role for clay soil. The result shows that the existence of a sandy layer is beneficial for the CBR value of clayey soil. The larger CBR was obtained at the deeper sandy layer in the proctor mold with higher drainage of clay excess pore water [7].

Cabalar and Karabash [8] studied the use of crushed rock mixed with tire buffings and cement as a sub-base material for road construction. They showed that the CBR values of the specimens with 3% cement and 5% tire buffings, 5% cement, and 5%, 10%, and 15% tire buffings were found to be greater than the CBR value of the clean sub-base gravel. They suggested the use of tire buffings and cement together as an alternative method to both reduce the construction cost and improve the CBR value of sub-base material in a flexible pavement design.

Bawadi et al. [9] carried out random inclusion of banana fiber at Malaysia to improve clay soil properties. They used banana fibers of 0.3%, 0.5%, and 1% by weight of soil as soil reinforcement in influencing the strength of clay soil and conducted unconsolidated undrained triaxial and CBR tests. The results show that 1% fiber gave the highest CBR and the highest shear strength under different cell pressures.

Chen et al. [10] studied the evaluation of the strength behavior of soft Shanghai clay by polypropylene fiber. The result shows that fiber additives can significantly improve the strength and ductility of cement-treated Shanghai clay. The fiber-reinforced cement clay reached its peak strength at a fiber content of 0.5%, and the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) will slowly reverse if the fiber content continues to increase. Even though the polypropylene fiber works better than the fiber bundles, the difference is less than 5%.

Mirzababaei et al. [11] investigated the addition of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) fiber used as a solution with concentrations of 0.1%, 0.3%, 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5%, and butane tetracarboxylic acid (BTCA) as a cross-linking agent at concentration rates of 0.1%, 0.3%, and 0.5% on the mechanical behavior of a clay soil. The result shows that the fiber reinforcement outperformed PVA-BTCA stabilization for clays with the lower initial void ratio. PVA-BTCA stabilization was however found to be superior to fiber reinforcement in clays with a relatively higher initial void ratio.

The series of multistage drained reverse direct shear tests were carried out on soft clay samples reinforced with 0.25% and 0.50% polypropylene fibers of 6, 10, and 19 mm in length. The result shows that fiber reinforcement resulted in a reduction of the compressibility of the soft clay at consecutive consolidation and shear stages. Although the effective internal friction angle of the soft clay was not altered significantly with the fiber reinforcement, the effective

cohesion of the soft clay improved significantly as much as 6.4 and 8.5 times with the inclusion of 0.25% and 0.50% of 10-mm-long fibers, respectively [12].

The performance of weak subgrade soil at random mixing of katcha and tef straw fiber was studied on the selected road section of Wolaita, Southwestern Ethiopia. Both fibers were prepared from 0.25% to 1.25% by dry weight of soil with an increment of 0.25% and 60 mm length. The result shows that the value of soaked CBR increases from 2.1% to 5.4% for katcha fiber-stabilized soil at 1% of fiber content and 4.4% for tef straw fiber mix at 0.75% [13].

The random distribution of fibers mobilizes fiber–soil adhesive bonding, which utilizes additional composite strength, and the interaction of flexible fibers behaves as a structural mesh that holds the soil together which increases the soil structural integrity. Moreover, kerosene coating physically prevents the entry of moisture into the katcha fiber, and it makes fiber more durable in addition to the natural content of hemicellulose (19%–22.47%) and lignin (5%–6.88%) [2, 14–16].

According to the literature, the effect of natural fibers and natural sand on clayey soil in terms of CBR and UCS is limited. The present study is primarily aimed at investigating the effect of katcha fibers as sustainable materials on the mechanical characteristics of subgrade soil used for construction purposes. The CBR and UCS of the unreinforced and reinforced subgrade soil with and without katcha fiber are investigated to determine the optimum content of two basic parameters (fiber content and fiber lengths). Based on test results, conclusions have been drawn for the material mix, costs, and its applicability for subgrade pavement.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Soil. The soil was collected from a site called Koye Feche project 18 road project which is located in the southeastern part of Addis Ababa city in Lemi Kura subcity; in terms of geographical coordinates, the site extends from 8°53'00" north to 8°54'30" north latitude and 38°48'45" east 38°50'15" east longitude.

The soil sample was extracted at a depth of 1.2 m from test pit 1 and test pit 2 as shown in Figure 1. The index property test was conducted in accordance with the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM-D2216) [18]. The geotechnical property of the soil is shown in Table 1. According to the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) classification system, the natural soil is classified as A-7-5 (35).

2.2. Katcha Fiber. Katcha is one of a well-known and easily available natural fiber in Ethiopia. The fiber was almost white in color; it is purchased from the local market of Gurage Zone, Aklil, and Moher woreda specifically from Dengez Kebele. The katcha fiber was selected from other locally available natural fibers because it was abundant and a viable natural resource than other natural fibers and has good tensile strength that was comparable with other natural fibers which were shown in Figure 2. The katcha fiber was conducted in accordance with the ASTM-D3822 [19]. The property of katcha fiber is shown in Table 2.

FIGURE 1: Map of the study area with location test pit (Koye Feche Google Map) [17].

TABLE 1: Geotechnical properties of soils.

Test type	Soil test results	
	Test pit 1	Test pit 2
NMC (%)	25.51	22.9
Specific gravity	2.73	2.78
Liquid limit (%)	75.40	70.40
Plastic limit (%)	44.60	44.60
Plastic index (%)	30.80	25.80
Clay (%)	39.71	7.39
Silt (%)	48.00	25.76
Sand (%)	7.07	48.84
Gravel (%)	5.17	18.00
Percent passing no. 200 sieve	87.77	33.15
AASHTO classification	A-7-5 (35)	A-2-7 (3)
Unified soil classification	MH	SM
MDD (%)	1.4	1.47
OMC (%)	30.3	28.75
CBR (%)	1.76	2.11
Percent swell (%)	7.46	7.00

Abbreviations: AASHTO, American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials; CBR, California Bearing Ratio; MDD, maximum dry density; MH, medium plastic; NMC, natural moisture content; OMC, optimum moisture content; SM, silty sand.

2.3. *Natural Sand.* The river sand was collected from a local market at Addis Ababa. Gradation and the specific gravity of sand were determined in the laboratory. The grain size varies from 0.1 to 4.5 mm, and 95.98% was typically coarse sand.

The sand used for this study was subangular in shape. Three percentages of sand were employed for reinforcement (10%, 15%, and 20%) by dry weight of the soil in order to improve the property of the soil. The particle size distribution of soil is shown in Figure 3.

2.4. *Methods.* The laboratory test was carried out in accordance with the ASTM and the Ethiopian Road Authority (ERA) standards, and the methodology was customized [20] for the experimental program as shown in the Table 3. The procedure was divided in to three steps:

- i. The properties of the clay soil, sand, and katcha were identified. The laboratory test such as sieve analysis test, consistency test, and modified compaction test and CBR tests were conducted for clay soil. In addition to that, gradation and consistency tests were also conducted for sand, and specific gravity and moisture content of katcha fiber were determined for both kerosene-coated and kerosene-uncoated katcha fiber which are shown in Figure 4.
- ii. At a fiber length of 20 mm, the weak subgrade clay soil (WSCS) was reinforced with 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% katcha fiber. And also, at a fiber length of 35 mm, the soil was reinforced with 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% katcha fiber, and finally, at a fiber length of 50 mm, the soil was reinforced with 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% katcha fiber as shown in Table 3. The mixing process was carried out for each variation manually, and the optimum fiber content and fiber length were determined from CBR test.

FIGURE 2: Photographic view: (a) enset plant and (b) katcha fiber.

TABLE 2: Property of katcha fiber.

Fiber property	Fiber condition	
	Uncoated fiber	3-day kerosene-coated fiber
Diameter (mm)	0.128	0.128
Specific gravity (Gs)	1.12	1.12
Moisture content (MC) (%)	12.30	11.10
Moisture regain (MR) (%)	13.64	11.36

FIGURE 3: Particle size distribution of sand.

iii. At 10% sand, the weak subgrade soil was mixed with optimum fiber content and optimum fiber length. And also at 15% sand, the weak subgrade soil was mixed with optimum fiber content and optimum fiber length, and

finally at 20% sand, the weak subgrade soil was mixed with optimum fiber content and optimum fiber length. Then, the optimum content of katcha fiber, kerosene, and sand was determined based on CBR and UCS test results.

TABLE 3: Experimental program.

Soil mixed with fiber and sand	Percentage (%)		
	Weak subgrade clay soil (WSCS)	Katcha fiber (KF)	Natural sand (SA)
100 WSCS + 0 KF + 0 SA	100	0	0
90 WSCS + 0 KF + 10 SA	90	0	10
85 WSCS + 0 KF + 15 SA	85	0	15
80 WSCS + 0 KF + 20 SA	80	0	20
89 WSCS + 1 KF + 10 SA	89	1	10
84 WSCS + 1 KF + 15 SA	84	1	15
79 WSCS + 1 KF + 20 SA	79	1	20

FIGURE 4: Photographic view of (a) katcha fiber soaking; (b) air-dried kerosene-soaked and kerosene-uns soaked katcha fiber; and (c) 35 mm length katcha fiber and sand.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effect of Sand on the Index Property of Soil. The particle size distribution of soil and soil–sand mix (10%, 15%, and 20%) is shown in Figure 5. The result shows that the percent of sand increases from 10% to 20% with increase in the contents of gravel, sand, and fines significantly.

Figure 6 displays the Casagrande plasticity chart illustrating the characteristics of soil and soil–sand mixtures (10%, 15%, and 20%). Analysis reveals a decrease in the liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), and plasticity index (PI) of the soils as the sand content increases from 0% to 20%. This reduction can be attributed to the decrease in the percentage of fines, which contribute to the soil's plasticity, as a result of sand incorporation. Notably, the addition of 20% sand proves effective in improving the workability of the soil, evident in the decrease of the PI from 30.80% to 21.11%.

The volumetric shrinkage and specific gravity of soil and soil–sand mix (10%, 15%, and 20%) are shown in Table 4. The volumetric shrinkage test was conducted with the ASTM-D427 [21]. The result shows that as the percent of sand increased from 0% to 20%, the volumetric shrinkage decreases from 18.15% to 7.05%.

3.2. Effect of Kerosene on WAC on Katcha Fiber. The variation of kerosene on WAC on katcha fiber at fiber length of 20, 35, and 50 mm for different water absorption capacities is

shown in Figure 7. The water absorption with kerosene test was carried out in accordance with the ASTM-D3822 [19]. The results shows that the length of fiber increases the WAC of fiber also; for the same soaking duration, the WAC increases as the length of fiber increases; for instance, for 2-day soaked katcha fiber, the WAC reduces from 55.435% to 50.240% as the fiber length increases from 20 to 50 mm. Similar behavior was also observed in the research of kerosene-coated coir fiber-reinforced expansive soil [4]. Based on the WAC test, 3 days of kerosene soaking of the fiber was selected for reinforcement since the least WAC was found for 3 days of kerosene soaking of katcha fiber.

3.3. Effect of Katcha Fiber on Compaction Characteristics of Soil. The modified compaction tests were conducted by mixing katcha fiber of lengths 20, 35, and 50 mm with WSCS at fiber content of 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% by dry weight. Nine combinations were studied. Different equipment including mold with 101.6 mm average inside diameter, a height of 116.4 mm, and a volume of 944 cm³, manually operated rammer with 4.54 kg free falling from 457 mm height, sample extruder, balance, 4.75 mm opening sieves, mixing tools, and plastic bags were the main equipment which were used in the laboratory. Similar compaction techniques were used in previous investigations [22]. The soil samples and soil samples mixed with fiber and sand are shown in Figure 8.

FIGURE 5: Particle size distribution of the natural soils and soil-sand mix.

FIGURE 6: The Casagrande plasticity chart of soil and sand mixed soils.

TABLE 4: Volumetric shrinkage and specific gravity test results for soil and soil-sand mix.

Soil mixture	Shrinkage limit (%)	Specific gravity (Gs)
100 WSCS + 0 SA	18.15	2.73
90 WSCS + 10 SA	14.36	2.62
85 WSCS + 15 SA	11.39	2.64
80 WSCS + 20 SA	7.05	2.59

Abbreviations: SA, natural sand; WSCS, weak subgrade clay soil.

FIGURE 7: Effect of kerosene soaking on water absorption capacity of katcha fiber.

FIGURE 8: Photographic view of (a) dry mix of soil and katcha fiber and (b) remold soil sample of reinforced soil.

The dry density–water content relationship of reinforced soil with fiber for different percentages of fiber as 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% at a fiber length of 20, 35, and 50 mm is shown in Figure 9. The modified compaction test was carried out by the ASTM-D1557 [23]. The result shows that the optimum moisture content (OMC) increases with the decrease in maximum dry density (MDD) for various fiber content and fiber length. At a fiber content of 0.5%, the dry density decreases from 1.39 to 1.35 kg/cm² with the increase in fiber length from 20 to 50 mm. At a fiber length of 50 mm, the dry density decreases from 1.35 to 1.30 kg/cm² with an increase in fiber content from 0.5% to 1.5%. Similar findings were also observed in different literatures that study the natural fiber-reinforced soil [24, 25].

3.4. Effect of Katcha Fiber on CBR. Figure 10 shows the effect of fiber content with its fiber length on the CBR values of the reinforced specimen. The CBR test was carried out by the ASTM-D1883 [26]. The fiber content varies from 0.5% to 1.5% with an increase in 0.5% considering the fiber length of (20, 35, and 50 mm). The result shows that the CBR increased from 3.5% to 5% with a decrease in fiber length from 50 to 35 mm at 1% fiber content. Similar studies also revealed that the effect of natural fibers on the CBR value of treated soil was greater than that of natural soil [9, 27]. The CBR value greater than 2% [20] was attained by reinforcing the soil at all percent of fiber content and the optimum content of the CBR value was obtained at 1% of fiber content with 35 mm length of fiber. The percent increase in the CBR

FIGURE 9: Variation of dry density with water content for soil and reinforced soil.

FIGURE 10: Variation of California Bearing Ratio (CBR) with fiber content for reinforced soil.

value from 189.2% to 240.91% from reinforced soil (1% and 35 mm fiber) to reinforced soil was mixed with 20% of sand, respectively.

3.5. Effect of Katcha Fiber on Swell. The percent swell–fiber length relationship of reinforced soil at the fiber content of 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% with a fiber length of 20, 35, and 50 mm

FIGURE 11: Variation of percent swell with fiber length of reinforced soil.

is shown in Figure 11. The swell test was carried out by the ASTM-D1883 [26]. The result shows that the katcha fiber has decreased the percent swell value from 7.46% to 5.00% with an increase in fiber content from 0% to 1%. The results are consistent with the findings of previous investigations [6, 28]. It is also noted that a 5% minimum swell value required for pavement subgrades was thus attained by 1% and 35-mm length reinforced soil samples. The percent decrease in swell from 32.17% to 35.66% from the reinforced soil (1% and 35 mm fiber) to the reinforced soil was mixed with 20% of sand, respectively.

3.6. Effect of Katcha Fiber and Sand on UCS. The UCS test was conducted for native soil, reinforced soil with the optimum amount of katcha fiber, and sand and fiber mixed soil. The sample of pure soil and 1% and 35 mm reinforced soil is shown in Figure 12.

The variation of stress with strain has been plotted for soil, reinforced soil, and reinforced soil with 20% of sand. The UCS test was carried out by the ASTM-D2166 [29]. The optimum mix is the mix having the highest UCS values for the given condition which is found to be 1% of fiber content with 35 mm of fiber length and 20% of sand. For the subgrade soil, the UCS value is 315.36 kPa, and this value increased to 503.82 kPa for 1% of fiber content with 35 mm of fiber length and 10% of sand.

The result shows that the UCS of soil is found to be 315.36 kPa and the highest UCS was recorded as 503.82 kPa for reinforced soil by 1%, 35 mm katcha fiber as shown in Figure 13. It was also shown that the peak tensile strength of fiber-reinforced soil was higher than that of unreinforced soil, and with increasing fiber length, the amount of peak tensile strength increased [30]. The addition of sand to reinforced soil reduces the interlock between the soil particles and the soil fiber interaction, and as a result, lower value of UCS was recorded, but this value of mixed soil is greater than that of the native soil. This increase in the strength of the soil was

FIGURE 12: Photographic view of (a) pure soil; (b) 1% and 35-mm reinforced soil; and (c) tensile strength test of katcha fiber of 600 mm length.

FIGURE 13: Stress–strain curve of soil and reinforced soil.

TABLE 5: Construction cost of subgrade without katcha fiber (conventional subgrade).

No.	Description	Unit	Quantity	Unit price (ETB)	Total price (ETB)
1	Site clearance				
1.2	Clearing and grubbing	m ²	7000	20	140,000
2	Earth work				
2.1	In layer thickness of 200 mm or less	m ³	1400	120	168,000
2.2	In layer thickness of exceeding 200 mm	m ³	7000	320	2,240,000
3	Backfilling				
3.1	Using selected backfill material	m ³	7000	375	2,625,000
4	Road bed preparation and compaction				
4.1	Compaction to 95% of modified AASHTO density	m ³	7000	175	1,225,000
	Total (ETB)	—	—	—	6,398,000

Abbreviations: AASHTO, American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials; ETB, Ethiopian birr.

TABLE 6: Construction cost of subgrade using reinforced excavated material.

No.	Description	Unit	Quantity	Unit price (birr)	Total price (birr)
1	Site clearance				
1.2	Clearing and grubbing	m ²	7000	20	140,000
2	Earth work				
2.1	In layer thickness of 200 mm or less	m ³	1400	120	168,000
3	Backfilling				
3.1	Katcha fiber	kg	70,000	16	1,120,000
3.2	Sand	m ³	1400	200	280,000
3.3	Kerosene	L	40,000	21.50	860,000
4	Road bed preparation and compaction				
4.1	Compaction to 95% of modified AASHTO density	m ³	7000	175	1,225,000
	Total (ETB)	—	—	—	3,793,000

Abbreviations: AASHTO, American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials; ETB, Ethiopian birr.

due to the addition of sand to reinforced soil that reduces the interlock between the soil particles and the soil fiber interaction, and as a result, lower value of UCS was recorded, but this value of mixed soil is greater than that of the native soil.

3.7. Cost Comparisons of Katcha Fiber-Reinforced Subgrade and Conventional Subgrade Soil. The cost of road construction may vary depending on a few factors including the topography, soil condition, machinery used, skilled and unskilled labor, machinery used, and road standards for particular projects [31]. The cost of subgrade pavement calculated with and without katcha fiber reinforcement considering 1 km road with the removal of top soil to a depth of 20 mm, with the initial cost of 16 m³ sand, was 3200 Ethiopian birr (ETB), and 4 L of kerosene was used for soaking 7 kg katcha fiber.

A comparison is made of the present study material cost with the conventional material for subgrade pavement. The total cost of construction was 6,398,000 ETB/km (Table 5) and 3,793,000 ETB/km (Table 6), without and with katcha fiber reinforcement, respectively. The result shows that the overall cost decreased to 2,605,000 ETB/km due to reinforcing the weak subgrade soil with 1% and 35 mm katcha fiber mixed with 20% sand [31].

4. Conclusions

To improve the WSCS collected from the Koye Feche road project in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, natural fiber (katcha), kerosene, and sand have been used. From the study findings, the following conclusions can be drawn: Various percentages of katcha fiber content (0.5%, 1%, and 1.5%) and lengths (20, 35, and 50 mm) were tested, revealing an optimal mix of 1% katcha fiber content, 35 mm fiber length, and 20% sand content, determined based on achieving maximum UCS. This optimized mix resulted in a decrease in plasticity to 31.46% and an increase in strength to 59.75% compared to untreated subgrade clay soil. Additionally, the CBR improved by 240% compared to the untreated soil. Cost savings were observed with the soil—1% katcha fiber content, 35 mm fiber length, and 20% sand mix compared to conventional replacement methods. These findings are anticipated to positively influence

the utilization of katcha fiber-reinforced subgrade soil pavement, offering valuable guidance for future road construction projects. Further research is recommended to explore the biochemical properties of katcha fiber, establish proportioning guidelines for Katcha fiber and sand application as soil stabilizers, and investigate the durability and lifespan of katcha fiber within soil masses, considering its effects on both soil and surrounding environments, including the impact of kerosene on biochemical composition and physical properties.

Data Availability Statement

The data used to support the study are available from the corresponding author upon request (argaw.asha@astu.edu.et or bethelgetamesay73@gmail.com).

Disclosure

A preprint has previously been published in Adama Science and Technology University as part of the thesis work [31].

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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